

FACTORS AFFECTING THE INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract. *In this article, the identification of factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise and the systematization of its classification signs, natural-climatic, social, financial-economic, industrial-technological, scientific-technical and organizational-management groups are considered.*

Keywords: *industrial enterprises, innovation, factor, activity, process, development.*

INTRODUCTION. In modern conditions, innovative activity is becoming the main condition for increasing the efficiency of organizations. The world's leading companies justify their success as the key to maintaining a high level of efficiency by constantly introducing innovations, that is, they believe that innovation management is the main task of the company. Missing the opportunity to use innovations shows that the enterprise cannot adapt to the external environment and, as a result, leads to failure. Today's situation shows that the external environment of enterprises is associated with a high degree of mobility and uncertainty, which indicates a high level of danger and risk. But giving up on innovation carries even higher risks

The formation and development or change in the level of innovative activity of enterprises occurs as a result of the influence of certain factors. During the objective and comprehensive research of the management of innovative activities of the enterprise, the problem of identifying and systematizing the factors affecting it will be urgent and insufficiently developed.

By the factor of innovative activity, we understand the conditions, reasons and indicators that affect the speed and description of the innovative growth of the enterprise. In this case, the innovative process takes place as a result of the interaction of many factors.

Analysis of literature on the topic The analysis of scientific literature shows that the classification of factors affecting innovative activity was not developed at the same time. Many authors have focused their attention on the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise. T.G. In her book, Filosofova noted the following factors that hinder innovation in industrial enterprises:

- lack of economic - financial resources, low funding from the state, high costs for innovation promotion, high level of economic risk, long period of innovation returns;

- production - lack of qualified personnel, lack of necessary information about new technologies, sales markets, inability of the organization to quickly adopt innovations, lack of well-established cooperation with other organizations, enterprises and scientific organizations;

- low price demand by consumers for innovative products, lack of sufficient legal and regulatory frameworks and regulation in innovative activities, insufficient stimulation of innovative activities by the state, poorly developed innovative infrastructure, lack of development in the technology market.

Another scientist, A.A. Bovin cites and analyzes the following factors influencing the innovation environment of the organization:

- social infrastructure (employees' access to services in educational, medical and cultural facilities);
- communication field (possibility of using communication, information resources);
- natural - geographical conditions (availability of transport, material and technical, energy, fuel and raw materials resources);
- technological and scientific-technical field (availability of the development market, availability of scientific-research institutes, etc.);
- economic and financial sphere (state support of innovative activities at the national and regional level, presence of investors interested in innovative developments);
- political-legal sphere (existence of national, regional plans and programs in the legal regulation of the innovative and scientific-technical sphere);
- strategic coverage of business (speed of innovation in a certain segment of the market);
- labor market.

In our opinion, the presented classifications cover only a small part of the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise. It should be noted that the factors that directly affect innovative activity have not been identified in the scientific literature.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. The main goal of this plan of our research is to determine the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise and the systematization of its classification marks. In our opinion, it is appropriate to classify the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise according to a number of signs. As a result of the conducted research, according to the level of manageability, the following classification signs of the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise were proposed.

According to the sources of origin, factors are divided into natural-climatic, social, financial-economic, industrial-technological, scientific-technical and organizational-management groups.

Natural and climatic factors have a great influence on the results of innovative activities of industrial enterprises. The availability of water supply, favorable climate, working conditions and availability of large sources of fuel and raw materials greatly contribute to the development of innovative activity of the enterprise and the growth of innovative activity.

Complexity of natural and climatic conditions, lack of labor force, production forces, low level of transport development, on the contrary, hindering the development of innovative activity of the enterprise, together with the fact that the enterprise requires a lot of money for the solution of the above-mentioned problems that have a negative effect on the level of innovative activity.

Social factors include the demographic situation, the level of social tension, the living conditions of workers, health care at the enterprise, the organization of sports and cultural activities, the general cultural and educational level of personnel, and others. These serve to ensure the effective and full use of the company's production resources, corporate development and formation of human capital.

Financial and economic factors determine the availability of funds, raw materials, and the level of opportunities to attract additional funds. Researching the financial and economic factors

of innovative activity, first of all, provides an opportunity to research the financial capabilities of the enterprise in the innovative development, to develop the direction of the innovative strategy development in the current and future financial situation of the company.

Industrial-technological factors determine the effective and full use of the company's production resources and technologies.

The transfer of ITTKI to scientific and technical factors covers the existence of intellectual property.

The analysis of organizational and management factors helps to determine the level of development of the innovation infrastructure, effective innovation management, marketing strategy in the implementation of innovations, the organization of innovation financing, and the suitability of the organizational structure to the tasks of innovative activity.

In our opinion, it is necessary to classify the factors affecting innovative activity according to another characteristic, the level of management.

When classifying the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise according to the level of management, it is possible to emphasize the factors that directly or indirectly affect the enterprise, as well as the level of its innovative activity and the factors that the enterprise cannot influence.

Based on the above, the classification of innovative activity factors according to the level of management is the most important when considering issues of expanding and evaluating the level of innovative activity of the enterprise.

Also, the factors affecting innovative activity are classified according to the level of management as follows:

- unmanaged;
- indirectly controlled;
- directly controlled.

Uncontrollable factors (or given) are factors that do not affect the innovative activity of the enterprise, the adoption of management decisions. Uncontrollable factors include:

- economic development trends;
- socio-economic situation in the region, state;
- innovation policy of the state;
- description of competition in certain markets;
- stable changes in the consumer system;
- the impact of international competition and division of labor;
- consumer payment options.

Indirectly controlled factors - these are the factors that affect the innovative activity of the enterprise, how management decisions are made, the factors related to the influence of external factors, and we can include the following:

- organizations financing innovative activities of the enterprise;
- availability of demand for an innovative product.

The influence of factors that indirectly control the development of the innovative activity of the enterprise is related to the management decisions of financial institutions that influence innovative projects, the state policy in the field of innovation, and the industrial systems of stakeholders in the promotion of innovation (banking sector, state investors, etc.).

Among the directly controlled factors, we present the factors that are completely related to the adoption of management decisions on the results of influencing the innovative activity of the enterprise.

Let's consider a group of directly controlled factors:

- the enterprise belongs to the industry;
- enterprise scale;
- human capital of the enterprise;
- socio-psychological environment in the enterprise;
- motivation system;
- achieved production and technological level;
- achieved scientific and technical degree;
- compliance of organizational management structures with tasks of the innovation process;
- innovative management system;
- financial resources of the enterprise.

The innovative activity of the enterprise is particularly influenced by its affiliation to the industry. It creates conditions for attracting private, local and foreign investors. In other similar circumstances, it is precisely the factor of belonging to which sector that increases the scale of investment attraction.

The size of the enterprise has a significant impact on the formation and level of innovative activity. Relatively larger enterprises have more opportunities to create departments engaged in scientific research and development, implementation of innovations. According to the statistical books, the main share of industrial production organizations is a group of enterprises with a large number of employees. The share of groups of enterprises with a small number of employees in the technological implementation of innovations is significantly lower. In order to form an organizational and management activity as an integral part of the innovative activity of the enterprise, it is necessary to match the management of the organizational system with the tasks of the innovative process. This factor includes:

- level of formalization of current organizational structures;
- innovative freedom of individual employees and departments;
- the possibility of forming target working groups;
- the existence of departments in the organizational structure that carry out innovation processing activities;
- the presence of departments in the organizational structure that implement the innovative activities of the enterprise.

The management of the processes of forming and creating innovative activities of the enterprise is carried out by the innovative management system.

The scale of the enterprise's financial resources should allow carrying out specific activities to carry out ITTKI, to modernize the main funds, to train and improve the skills of personnel, to activate them, and to increase the level of innovative activity of the enterprise.

In our opinion, the results of the research will create conditions for the development of complex indicators that allow to determine and implement the level of innovative activity of the enterprise and, as a result, to improve the methods of evaluating the innovative activity of industrial enterprises.

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